

The Status of Work Life Balance of Women's Employment in Primary Education Sector and Its Impact on Their Perception of Work in Bangladesh: A Study on Khulna City

Md. Abdullah Al Mamun

Abstract:

The primary education sector is one of the most prosperous sectors in Bangladesh and most of the teachers in this field are women. This study looked specifically at the state of the working life balance of women in the field of teaching and its impact on their perceived performance. Data have been collected among the 130 women educators currently working in various governments and at the kinder school in Bangladesh. A structured questionnaire was used to collect samples from participants. Phase data is summarized using frequency distribution, bivariate analysis performed on chi-square test and multiple liner retrieval is used to identify potential variations associated with perceived performance. The average age was 40-50 y (about 50%) followed by 38.5% it was 30-40 years. 31.5% had more than 2 dependencies. Of them, 57.17% were satisfied with the actual work, 24.87% were neutral and 10% disagreed with their performance. The results of the various organizations showed that age (p -value = 0.002), dependency number (p -value = 0.002), marital status (p -value = 0.006), institutional types (p -value = 0.004) were significantly different depending on their performance. However, the variance was not found in terms of working age. Research has shown that most professionals are satisfied with their performance, however, one in ten thinks they are not performing satisfactorily. Evidence shows that with the reduction of workload per hour, work structures from the organization can speed up the performance of professionals.

Keywords: Work life Balance, Perceive Performance, Primary education, Women Participation, Teaching staffs.

IJSB
Accepted 25 October 2020
Published 28 October 2020
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4146895

About Author (s)

Md. Abdullah Al Mamun, Lecturer in Finance Department of Business Administration, North Western University, Khulna, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Balancing work and health has always been a concern for those interested in the quality of working life and its connections and the quality of border health. The balance of work life is that communication between work and therefore other activities with family, community, recreation and private development. It is about the right or limited combination of a person's participation in work and other aspects of his or her life and this combination does not always remain the same and can be changed over time. Employee health balance is when conflicts between occupational health and personal health are reduced by having appropriate policies, programs, supportive management and provision in the workplace and positive relationships in personal life. Employee performance and job satisfaction are said to affect the employee's health balance. Employee health balance helps to reduce the level of stress in the workplace and increase job satisfaction. Companies have recognized the importance of the employee's life balance and product indicators as well as the professionalism of the employees. Employers offer a variety of programs such as flexible hours, shifts, team visits, child care centers, health care centers, etc. to encourage employees to work effectively. Employees feel motivated and honest and committed to the job because it makes more effort to provide a healthy balance between work and health. Unions face many challenges in implementing policies on Workplace Health Standards as workers today not only look at work but also want the organization to take advantage of their well-being. Organizations are therefore implementing new policies in which employees can give time to enjoy and spend time with their family. This current research paper aims to study the balance of occupational health in the workplace of women especially in the primary education sector in the Khulna section.

2. Literature review:

In Bangladesh, the problems becoming more burning and most debated one. Organizations and employees are complaining about one another to not be up to the mark because the demand of the business. (Arif & Farooqi, 2014). Work life balance is perceived because the flexible working environment that supports to accomplish both the working duties and private life responsibilities (Saltzstein et al., 2001). Work-life balance has implication on employee attitudes, behaviors, wellbeing still as organizational effectiveness (Cropanzano et al., 1997). Thus Work-life balances are practices that are meant to assist employees better manage their work and non-working times which is able accomplish the worker personal life goals together with organizational goals (Avey et al., 2011). Found that there's a powerful relation between work-based support for girls with their job satisfaction and organizational goals accomplishment (Marcinkus et al., 2007). The manager's support isn't a significant issue just in case of influencing work-life balance rather pleasant working atmosphere plays a big role in achieving the required objectives of the workers (Bhalerao, 2013). While the difficulty of balancing between work-life has acquire the lime light, the fact is, employees are constantly juggling between to stay a balance between their professional and private life (Bell et al., 2012). In keeping with Tomazevic et al. (2014) the meaning of work-life balance is to effectively combining calling with professional life with personal obligations and creates a harmony between these two aspects. They have also discussed both positive and negative consequences as a results of both work-life balance and work-life imbalance. If there's balance in work-life, employees get motivation and job satisfaction increases while imbalance create dissatisfaction among employees. The sensation of stress and overwork found if there is imbalance between work-life. Furthermore human resource department should promote

policies, which incorporates corporate social responsibility, employee well-being and work-life balance (Bell et al., 2012). Most of the working women are balancing their work life with personal life management, in some cases it is found that they are depriving of social interaction, not having enough time to think about their work and not getting time to engage themselves in leisure that they are wishing for (Hasan and Hossain, 2018). The nature of the workplace today is affected by different family and work-related factors (Hossain et al., 2019).

In the perspective of Bangladesh, female employees face more hurdles in balancing work and personal life than male employees (Sultana & Chatterjee, 2019). In this context, I have tried to identify the status and the impact of work-life balance on the performance of the women employee especially in the primary education sector in Khulna division. There have been lots of research in work-life balance of employees but from them, I have a little understanding about the association between work life balances with perceive performance in the primary education sector especially in Bangladesh. Since, in Bangladesh primary sector consists of a large number of women teachers give their service. That's why my research may contribute to a better understanding of the aforesaid aspect. The study focused on the subsequent two main objectives, to determine the status of work life balance of ladies employee working particularly in primary education sector in Khulna division and to assess the impact of work life balance on the perceive performance of ladies employee.

Thus, the current study focused on the subsequent two main objectives, to see the status of work life balance of women employee working particularly in primary education sector in Bangladesh. To understand the impact of work life balance on the perceive performance of women employee.

3. Methodology

A cross section study was conducted in Bangladesh. The set of study data was mainly collected from a Government teacher and Primary School in the city of Khulna, in the southern part of Bangladesh. I have collected information among female teachers currently employed under a separate primary school in Bangladesh. Research is the essence of experimentation. The proposed research data was collected from a questionnaire from 130 female respondents from various government and non-government primary schools.

Statistical analysis

Class variability is summarized by the distribution of statistics and continuous variance is summarized by descriptive statistics. Bi-Variates analyzes were performed on chi-square tests with accurate comparisons and independent sample t-tests for the definition of visual school performance.

Co-types

Respondents are selected on the basis of their gender, and the length of service they provide to organizations. This study aims to determine the status of occupational health of working women and to determine the effect of occupational health balance on their performance in the workplace. By using the questionnaire I have tried to hunt down the employee's health management, self-control, financial security, housekeeping management, caregivers and other relevant factors that support the employee's health balance. In addition, I have done artistic analysis showing how the balance of their working life affects their perceived performance.

Outcomes

The perceived performance of the work was the result of a study, which was measured on a Likert scale of 5 groups including strict disagreement, disagreement, neutrality, confession and firm consent. I re-divided and strongly disagreed with the disagreement and disagreement, and strongly agreed to agree.

Table-1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants

Variable	Label	Total=N (%)
Types of Institutions	Nationalized	90(69.2)
	Private	40(30.8)
Age	<30 y	18 (13.8)
	30-40 y	50 (38.5)
	41-50 y	42 (32.3)
	>50y	20 (15.4)
Marital status	Single	19 (14.6)
	Married	111 (86.4)
Number of dependents	0	18 (13.8)
	1	40 (30.8)
	2	31 (23.8)
	2+	41 (31.5)

Source: Author's Field study/ software output

4. Results

Basic features

In this proposed study, I employed 130 powers at Private (30.8%) and Public Primary schools (69.2%) in Bangladesh from the Khulna section. Of them, 38.5% were 40-50 years of age and most of the teachers (about 50%) were in the final phase of work (shown in table 1). In terms of household chores, 66.67% of participants participated in household chores, including cooking management (70%), procurement management (60%), household cleaning (70%) and family. In terms of child care and personal care, about half (40.5%) of the teacher pays close attention to the child; care for parents in law and children when they suffer from a physical ailment. In the case of self-regulation, only 37.4% of respondents feel that they have time to think about their job and take care of themselves. in terms of personal health satisfaction 46.93% satisfied work includes family travel (52.4%), contact with relatives (46.1%) and 42.3% of them can participate in community events.

When there is support from the family 62.33% of them feel they are getting the support they need including new programs, cooking services and payment of service bills by family members. In terms of workplace support approximately 54.14% of employees are satisfied with the views of their employers on their needs. In addition to the financial assistance from the office 56.15% of employees are happy with their goal which includes compensation policy and at the end of the service a financial security life. In terms of job satisfaction 57.17% of employees are satisfied with their workload, performance recognition and training methodology (Table 2).

Features that contribute to visual performance

I have created a bivariate relationship between teacher performance through their social work and other activities. The result showed that age (p-value = 0.002), dependency number (p-value = 0.002), marital status (p-value = 0.006), institutional types (p-value = 0.004) varied significantly according to their functionality. However, variances were not found in terms of working years (Table 3).

Table-2: Status of work-life balance of the participants

work-life balance of the participants	Mean(SD)	Disagree N (%)	Neutral N (%)	Agree N (%)
Managing household's chores				
Manage cooking of my family.	4.11 (.925)	6(4.6%)	31(23.8%)	36(27.7%)
Manage required shopping of my family members.	3.76 (1.077)	2 (1.5)	16 (12.3%)	37 (28.5%)
Complete my house cleaning with the help of paid maid.	3.96 (1.130)	23(17.7%)	16 (12.3%)	34 (26.2%)
Managing Children and Dependent care				
Give full attention towards children.	3.29 (1.395)	16 (12.3)	36 (27.7)	22 (16.9)
Taking care of aged parent(s)/in law(s) properly.	2.81 (1.301)	35 (26.9)	30 (23.1)	24 (18.5)
Take time off/leave when my children/dependents are suffering from illness.	3.24 (1.305)	23 (17.7)	32 (24.6)	32 (24.6)
Self- Management				
Have enough time to think, plan and to schedule my day-to-day activities.	3.26 (1.152)	19(14.6)	40 (30.8)	41 (31.5)
Have sufficient time to take care of myself.	2.95 (1.337)	37 (28.5)	25 (19.2)	26 (20.0)
Have time and energy to engage in any leisure activities that I want to do.	2.84 (1.206)	38 (29.2)	35 (26.9)	25 (19.2)
Personal Life Satisfaction				
Satisfied with the family trips I enjoy during vacation at least once in a year.	3.73 (1.359)	22 (16.9)	24 (18.5)	34 (26.2)
Satisfied about maintain regular contacts with my relatives.	3.42 (1.187)	25 (19.2)	39 (30.0)	28 (21.5)
Satisfied with my engagements in Social activities.	3.12 (1.274)	24 (18.5)	33 (25.4)	35 (26.9)
Support from Family				
Family members support my initiatives.	3.76 (1.212)	18 (13.8)	24 (18.5)	35 (26.9)
Can pay electricity, water and telephone bills through my family members.	3.78 (1.073)	8 (6.2)	50 (38.5)	23 (17.7)
Cooking activity is easier for me because I am getting support from family members.	3.78 (1.271)	22 (16.9)	8 (6.2)	45 (34.6)
Workplace Support				
All the employees are treated equally if they request assistance with work and family related matters.	3.68 (.924)	12 (9.2)	46 (35.4)	43 (33.1)
Can give my attention for urgent family or personal issues immediately.	3.64 (1.188)	30 (23.1)	33 (25.4)	21 (16.2)
Get high degree of respect and fair treatment from my boss.	3.70 (.986)	10 (7.7)	46 (35.4)	39 (30.0)
Financial Assistance from Office				
I am happy with my organization compensation policy.	3.56 (1.100)	11 (8.5)	38 (29.2)	46 (35.4)
I have financial security after ending my service life.	3.65 (1.441)	4 (3.1)	31 (23.8)	25 (19.2)
Sometimes, I solve my financial problems through my colleagues.	3.56 (1.441)	10 (7.7)	59 (45.4)	35 (26.9)
Work Satisfaction				
Feel satisfied with my working hours.	3.55 (1.415)	16 (12.3)	22 (16.9)	29 (22.3)
Feel satisfied with the recognition I get for good performance of work.	3.62 (1.067)	6 (4.6)	42 (32.3)	46 (35.4)
Feel satisfactory with the training when new systems are introduced in the organization.	3.62 (1.156)	17 (13.1)	33 (25.4)	38 (29.2)

Source: Author's Field survey

Multivariate analysis showed that age, number of dependents, family support, Personal Health Satisfaction had a negative impact on performance. On the other hand, the Year of Service, the number of dependents, the quality of household chores, child care and dependent care, personal health satisfaction and family support have a positive impact on the performance of teaching staff (Table 4).

Table-3: Participants characteristics according to the work performance

	Level	Performance				P-value
		2	3	4	5	
Types of Institutions	Nationalized	0	41	37	12	.004*
	Private	2	8	18	12	
Age, n (%)	<30 y	0	6	8	4	.002*
	30-40 y	2	27	21	0	
	41-50 y	.8	18.8	21.2	14	
	>50y	0	4	10	6	
Years of service	Less than 1	0	2	0	0	.150
	1-10	2	21	19	4	
	11-20	.7	17.3	19.5	16	
	Above 20	0	8	10	4	
	BDT > 30,0000	4(57.1)	13(59.1)	50(66.7)		
Marital status, n (%)	Single	0	0	12	7	.006*
	Married	2	49	41	17	
Number of dependents, n (%)	0	0	4	6	8	.002*
	1	2	12	24	2	
	2	0	11	15	5	
	>2	0	22	10	9	

Source: Author's Field survey

*Chi-square for categorical variables and ANOVAs for continuous co-variant; $p < 0.05$ as statistical significance

Table-4: Factors contributing to the work performance of the study participants (Multiple linear regression)

	Beta Coefficient	SE	95% CI	P-value
Types of Institutions	.020	.151	[-.268- .333]	.830
Age	-.077	.085	[-.232 - .104]	.453
Year of service	.150	.109	[-.062 - .372]	.160
Marital status	.000	.171	[-.339 - .339]	.999
Number of dependents	-.116	.065	[-.211 - .045]	.200
Managing household's chores	.1223	.076	[-.0666 - .239]	.325
Managing Children and Dependent care,	.002	.076	[-.149 - .154]	.649
Self- Management	.019	.066	[-.116 - .144]	.651
Personal Life Satisfaction	-.039	-.016	[-.142- .097]	.287
Support from Family	-.003	.069	[-.137 - .138]	.567
Workplace Support	.032	.077	[-.129 - .059]	.779
Financial Assistance from Office	.137	.074	[-.070 - .223]	.051
Work Satisfaction	.095	.078	[-.098 - .211]	.231

Source: Author's Field survey

*linear regression model; Statistical sig.

a. Dependent Variable: Rate your performance (your perception) in comparison to your capabilities (on a scale of 1-5), where 1 is the lowest and 5 is the highest: (Put tick mark)

5. Discussion and conclusion

The research paper focuses on determining the state of the working life of women workers and their impact on the practical performance of the Bangladesh primary education sector. After some data analysis it was found that most working women are less likely to interact with people, do not have enough time to think about themselves and their job and do not have

the time for the entertainment they desire. Overall they maintain a good balance between work life and personal health. The combination of the bivariate between the performance of educators in their social work and other activities was the result showed that the year of services, the moderate change in the management of household chores, self-regulation varied greatly in the way they work. The multivariate analysis showed that, the year of service, managing household chores at a satisfactory level, managing children and dependent care, self-regulation has a positive impact on the performance of teaching professionals. From the conclusion other recommendations that are beneficial to maintain a proper balance between occupational health and personal health can be recommended. Schools can use more flexibility in terms of providing more time for self-care to increase productivity and efficiency. Introduce opportunities for personal health satisfaction and is instrumental in achieving a workplace health balance.

This study has some limitations other than the various study outcomes it has encountered with the following specific limitations: the majority of respondents are from urban areas which also poses some inconsistencies; most respondents come from the age group of 40-50 who may not always provide true understanding; The total number of respondents is low compared to looking at the authenticity of the findings.

References:

- Arif, B. & Farooqi, Y. A. (2014). "Impact of work life balance on job satisfaction and Organizational commitment among university teachers: A case study of University of Gujrat, Pakistan,". 5, pp. 24-29.
- Avey, J. B. and Reichard, R. J., Luthans, F. & Mhatre, K. H. (2011). Meta-analysis of the impact of positive psychological capital on employee attitudes, behaviors, and performance,, *Human resource development quarterly*, vol. 22, pp. 127-152.
- Bell, A., Rajendran, D. and Theiler, S. (2012). Job Stress, Wellbeing, Work-Life Balance and Work-Life Conflict among Australian Academics. *Electronic Journal of Applied Psychology*, 8, 25-37.
- Bhalerao, S. K. (2013). WORK-LIFE BALANCE: THE KEY DRIVER OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT,. *ASM's International E-Journal of Ongoing Research in Management and IT*, pp. 1-9.
- Cropanzano, R., Howes, J. C., Grandey, A. A., & Toth, P. (1997). The relationship of Organizational politics and support to work behaviors, attitudes, and stress,". *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, vol. 18, , pp. 159-180.
- Hossain, G. M. S., Hossen, M. N., Rahman, M. S. & Hasan, M. (2019). Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) Approach to Examining the Factors' Affecting Work Life Balance among Female Teachers': An Empirical Study. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 3(6), 140-152. doi:doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3528458>
- Marcinkus, W. C., Whelan-Berry, K. S. & Gordon, J. R. . (2007). The relationship of social support to the work-family balance and work outcomes of midlife women. *Women in Management Review*, vol. 22, , pp. 86-111.
- Hasan, M. M. and Hossain, S. (2018). The Status of Work Life Balance for Women in Banking Sector and Its Impact on Their Perceive Performance in Bangladesh. *IIARD International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 4, 7.

- Sultana, R. & Chatterjee, R. (2019). Work-Life Balance: A Study on Female Workers in CEPZ. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 3(1), 195-203. doi: doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3372646>
- Saltzstein, A. L., Ting, Y. & Saltzstein, G. H. (2001). Work-family balance and job satisfaction: The impact of family-friendly policies on attitudes of federal government employees,". 61, 452-467.
- Tomazevic, N., Kozjek, T. and Stare, J. (2014). The Consequences of a Work-Family (Im) Balance: From the Point of View of Employers and Employees. 7, 83-100. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5539/ibr.v7n8p83>

Cite this article:

Md. Abdullah Al Mamun (2020). The Status of Work Life Balance of Women's Employment in Primary Education Sector and Its Impact on Their Perception of Work in Bangladesh: A Study on Khulna City. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 4(11), 93-100. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4146895>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/614.pdf>

Published by

